

From Poetry to Science, or From Rules to Theory¹

A Response to Oleg Donskikh's Article

"Language as an Indicator of The Visualization of Scientific Thinking" [1]

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Abstract

This article develops two theses: (1) science is one of the forms or spheres of cognition, alongside art, philosophy, religion, mathematics, and mysticism; (2) defining what science is can only be accomplished by drawing boundaries between these forms of cognition. It is noted that differences between cognitive spheres cannot be determined either by examining the history of their formation or at the level of their connection with language - all of them use language as the primary tool for recording the results of cognition. The basic criteria that ensure a relatively rigorous demarcation between science and other cognitive spheres are: the specificity of the object of cognition (reproducible or unique) and the structure of the text in which the result of cognition is recorded (rational or irrational).

Keywords: science, cognition, knowledge, language, philosophy

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I join the discussion on science initiated by Oleg Donskikh in his article "Language as an Indicator of The Visualization of Scientific Thinking," agreeing with some of the ideas presented, developing them, and disputing others.

First, let me outline my initial positions. Like Oleg Donskikh, I believe that thinking in general, and scientific thinking in particular, is inseparably connected with language. I define thinking as operating with notions for the purpose of constructing systems of notions (thoughts). It was precisely the development of language, the active exchange of signs, and especially the manipulation of signs within individual consciousness that made it possible to separate operations with notions from actions with objects. This ensured the emergence of thinking as an independent activity that does not require mandatory reliance on sensory input and behavioral activity.

However, it must be noted that this connection between thinking and language is not specific to science: all cognitive spheres - religion, art, science, philosophy - arose and function within

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the realm of language and formalize the results of cognition in the form of sign systems - texts. Moreover, one can question the very distinction of special types of thinking: scientific, religious, philosophical. Indeed, it is not uncommon for one person to work successfully in several cognitive spheres simultaneously. And it is difficult to assume that for writing a scientific work, a philosophical treatise, or a work of art, one uses different types of thinking. My own experience also suggests that the ways of operating with notions, while dependent on the sphere of activity, are not so different as to warrant distinguishing different types of thinking in various cognitive spheres. The difference between everyday thinking and cognitive thinking, however, is fundamental and is connected, as already noted, with the separation of thinking (operating with notions) from actions with objects.

It is important to note that for understanding the specificity of science, it is essential to indicate its distinction not so much from everyday, industrial, and other activities, but from other cognitive spheres, which also include art, philosophy, religion, mathematics, and mysticism. Cognition is an activity that ensures adaptation and better orientation of a person in the world. But not locally (here and now), but globally: the result of cognitive activity is not a specific consumer product or service, but behavioral scenarios (usually recorded in the form of texts) that generally increase human survivability in the world. And since the world is not reducible to physical reality alone, since a person lives primarily in a society with its value-based, ethical, aesthetic, and other relations, successful human functioning in a community of one's kind requires special methods and forms of cognition that are fundamentally different from scientific ones. And naturally, cognitive activities arise in society whose subjects are: aesthetic perception (art), unified forms of thinking (philosophy), universal values (religion), explicit structural unity (mathematics), and implicit unity of the world (mysticism). Thus, the task of delineating the boundaries of science can be reduced to indicating its differences from other cognitive activities [2].

Another principle that is important in investigating any subject, including science, in my view, is the strict distinction between its genesis and its actual (here and now) analysis. The history of the emergence and development of a subject does not always allow one to correctly identify the specificity of its contemporary existence or draw boundaries between it and other entities. For example, as I noted above, pointing to the linguistic roots of science will not help us formulate its difference from philosophy or religion. Nor will pointing to the historical fact that science branched off from philosophy. Science was never philosophy; more precisely, scientific knowledge was never philosophical knowledge - it is just that until a certain point, both philosophical and scientific statements were produced by the same people, who in pre-scientific times were called philosophers.

And now, after such a conceptually rich introduction, we can proceed directly to the discussion. Let me begin with the definition of science proposed by Oleg Donskikh: "*I will define science as an activity consciously directed toward obtaining new knowledge about a specific fragment of what appears to be reality.*" First, let us note the connection of science to so-called "reality." It is reasonable to assume that this indication is necessary to separate science from such

cognitive spheres as philosophy, religion, and mathematics, about which one cannot say that their subjects are fragments of reality. But on the other hand, do disciplines like linguistics or theology study fragments of reality? Moreover, the word "reality" has no fixed meaning - some philosophical schools reject the notion of "reality" altogether (for example, radical constructivism, not to mention subjective idealism). Therefore, I would suggest not using the word "reality" in definitions at all, especially since it can easily be replaced by indicating such a generally accepted feature of this reality as "unique reproducibility." Then the subject of scientific cognition should be recognized not as abstract reality, but as unambiguously reproducible phenomena, regardless of their ontological status. And this decision undoubtedly corresponds to general scientific ideas about the reproducibility of experiments and the possibility of recording the regularities identified in them in the form of rational sign systems (formulas, theories). Presenting unambiguously reproducible phenomena as the subject of science immediately draws a boundary between science and such cognitive activities as art, religion, philosophy, and mysticism, in which the subject is either unique (religion) or not reproducible in perception (philosophy, art, mysticism).

Now let us pay attention to the word "knowledge" used in the definition and ask a simple question: is all knowledge about reproducible phenomena scientific? Should all activity directed toward obtaining new knowledge be considered scientific? For example, statistical analysis of economic and other indicators, public opinion polls, etc., are clearly directed toward obtaining new knowledge - but such knowledge is not usually called scientific. Or cartographic and geological activities are clearly aimed at obtaining new knowledge about reproducible phenomena, but this knowledge is also not usually classified as scientific. That is, not everything about knowledge of fragments of reality, not everything that provides us with new knowledge about reproducible phenomena, can automatically be attributed to science.

So the question arises: what knowledge is scientific? And the answer to this question is given to us by Oleg Donskikh. But not in his initial definition of science, but in his reasoning about its gradual emergence from linguistic practice. Donskikh sees the first step in the "scientification" of subject knowledge in its formulation in the form of poetic texts, that is, *"such a conscious presentation of texts that requires knowledge of the rules of their regular organization"* (here and below, italics indicate quotations from Donskikh's text). What seems extremely important here is the indication of *"regular organization,"* that is, the identification of reproducible structures in the text. Poetic texts, as Donskikh emphasizes, *"require awareness of a set of rules,"* and moreover, *"language itself becomes the object of attention, unlike the situation with everyday speech."* It was precisely the identification of language - or more precisely, text as a subject of analysis - and the formation of notions not connected with the subject activity described in texts, but recording regularly reproducible linguistic structures, that directly led to the creation of the first scientific discipline - grammar. That is, grammar is not just knowledge about text as a fragment of reality, but knowledge of rules that record unambiguously reproducible regularities in text construction. At the same time, the rules must be formulated in terms specially created for this purpose.

Further, Donskikh notes that philosophy made a special contribution to the formation of scientific cognition, in which "a whole series of new words appears, allowing the formation of vocabulary in such a way that it makes it possible to express genus-species relations." While fully agreeing with this, I would still note that the main contribution of philosophy to the development of science lies not in "word creation," not in introducing new notions (being, cosmos, nature, infinity, logos, etc.) and not in "going beyond specific images to the level of reflection," but in using these new notions to construct complex, internally consistent structures that, when recorded in text, are called theories. Unlike grammar, which operates with individual rules, philosophy raised cognition to the level of constructing integral rational (logically consistent) systems of notions.

But philosophy itself, despite its theoretical character (logicality) and ability to record in structures of notions the regularities of its subject, that is, to produce knowledge about it, fundamentally cannot be classified as scientific activity. Since the subject of philosophy - the philosophical thinking of the philosopher - is not unambiguously reproducible, this subject is inaccessible for analysis by others. That is, one can verify the logic of a philosophical theory, reproduce its conclusions, but comparing these conclusions with its subject - the thinking of the philosopher - can only be done by the philosopher himself.

Science, as an independent cognitive activity, formed when it combined two linguistic practices, two textual forms of knowledge representation: (1) empirical statements about unambiguously reproducible phenomena and (2) theoretical statements, logically derived within a sign system that describes that phenomenon in scientific terms [3]. It is essential that neither empirical statements (for example, those obtained experimentally) nor the conclusions of a theory are scientific in themselves. They become scientific only when the results of observations coincide with the logical/mathematical conclusions of the theory. For example, sociological statistical data in themselves are merely empirical, not scientific knowledge. Similarly, a sociological theory, apart from and prior to confirmation, cannot be considered scientific. It becomes scientific only after its calculations coincide with the results of social measurements.

The interpretation of science as a cognitive activity that necessarily includes both theoretical and empirical components is applicable not only to the exact sciences but also to the humanities. A detailed analysis of a literary work or description of a historical event is difficult to consider scientific. But when a scholar has a theory and seeks and finds its confirmations in a writer's works or in documentary evidence, then such activity should certainly be called scientific - literary or historical. At the same time, for the humanities, there is clearly also the presence of unambiguously reproducible subjects (the original texts can be read by anyone) and theoretical conclusions whose logic can also be subjected to verification (although, of course, not as rigorous as in the exact sciences).

In conclusion, it remains to formally summarize all the conclusions obtained. Science is a cognitive activity whose subject is unambiguously reproducible phenomena and whose result is theories whose logical conclusions must be confirmed by empirical data (the nuances of the

relationship between verification and falsification of scientific theories require separate consideration). Such cognitive disciplines as religion, art, philosophy, and mysticism are not sciences because their subjects are not reproducible. Mathematics as a whole cannot be considered a science because its subject, although reproducible, is inseparable from the discipline itself, that is, there is no clear separation of theoretical and empirical statements in it.

References

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